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HEALTH MANAGEMENT:
REALIGNING SYSTEMS,
CONTEXTS AND PLAYERS

ABSTRACT BOOK

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European Public Health in the context of Green Deal - from COVID-19

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The Covid-19 pandemic crisis caused a serious 'tectonic' disturbance in all sectors, especially pointed out weaknesses of the healthcare systems. The recently adopted European Green Deal (EGD) should take into account the Covid-19 pandemic challenge and maintain its primary objectives. The pandemic crisis has shown not only individual health risks, but also global health threats (direct and indirect). The SARS-CoV-2 virus causes an insufficiently known infectious disease. The subsidiary health effects are still countless: mental health, health-economic costs, deadlock in the other diseases' treatment, etc.

One of the main messages regarding environment, is that society should find new economic models less damaging to the environment and to biodiversity, implying circular economy, a less consumerist and active society: e.g. a 4 days-working week. Covid-19 took us to the extreme of being confined at home, either working or taking care of our families. However, the Covid-19 global quarantine and confinement (and huge reduction of travelling, mainly flights) had a great impact on decrease of CO2 levels, on the quality of air and on biodiversity.

Vulnerability and lack of efficient action in many countries, is a strong warning for Europe (and globally) to insist in strengthening public health and convert lessons learned into action. The Coronavirus, originating from destruction of wildlife and intensive animal farming, will bring more pandemics in the future. We need more public health consideration towards effects of climate change on public health. It is possible to keep economy functioning by promoting remote work supported by digital platforms and innovation for international networks. Strategically, the European recovery plan should be aligned with the EGD. Public Health should be more engaged on studying future impacts of climate change on health care and at the same time should propose new models for healthy living in the line with sustainable circular economy.

Public Health should be more engaged on studying future impacts of climate change on health care. European Public Health should reflect about the COVID-19 impacts on Society and on its relation with Climate Change.